

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-6-64-IF-2% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	43	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 6 64
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	280.0nm
Run Time:	30.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 280.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/10/2023 4:39:13 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/19/2023 3:34:59 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.551	1184716	49.51	119914
2	7.944	1208255	50.49	114098

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-6-91-IF-2% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20231019
Vial:	17	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	123
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	280.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 280.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/19/2023 9:58:24 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/25/2023 8:07:48 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.584	133283	8.78	11392
2	7.992	1384535	91.22	108422